

St. Joseph's Restoration Project, Williams County (41.64808, -84.56440)

Since construction in 2021, researchers infer that the St. Joseph's Restoration Project has high nutrient retention potential due to the high concentration inputs it receives from agricultural drainage (up to 1.1 mg P/L). However, nutrients are primarily delivered during flooding events, so drought in 2024 and 2023 limited nutrient delivery. This Project's largest pool (B) experiences periods of low oxygen and high phosphorus concentrations. Current phosphorus budgets assume that those high concentrations of phosphorus are exported. The Project released 0.1 lbs P per acre in 2024, but the runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field (0.6 lbs P per acre each year) resulted in overall net phosphorus retention, and inorganic nutrient forms were retained (phosphate, nitrate, and ammonium). The vegetation stock was 903 lbs P per acre aboveground and 16 lbs P per acre belowground.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 33 acres of restored wetland, including multiple features: four tile-fed flowthrough pools (A, B, C, G), two of which also occasionally flood from an adjacent ditch (B, G); three depressional pools that function periodically as floodplains depending on water levels in the adjacent ditch or river (D, E, F); and the St. Joseph River. Water enters the Project via three drainage tiles discharging from upstream agricultural lands draining approximately 75 acres adjacent to the north and east of the Project. Water flows through the wetland features and exits into a ditch to the east. The ditch connects to the St. Joseph River, which flows west parallel to the south edge of the Project. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which flow is expected from the three input tiles (North, Northeast, Northwest). Floodplain events are defined as periods when water level in the East Ditch or the St. Joseph River exceed their banks and flow into the Project.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Vegetation at this Project suggests it is possible to have both high nutrient retention and high biodiversity. Managers may consider promoting biodiversity, such as by controlling Cattail or other invasive species, to maximize both nutrient retention and vegetation habitat quality.
- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, and/or ditch water inputs in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.